

Minutes EB24-03
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
17 June 2024 @ 7h00 (EST)

Attendance

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair, Reconciliation Commission
Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barny Whitman (BW)	- Chair

Apology

Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio
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1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

Session at the ASM meeting.

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

Action items from previous meeting

Ongoing action items

1. KK to follow-up on the NSF RCN and ICB funding

To follow-up.

2. PH to investigate the possibility of continued funding from ISME for work on the registry.

Decision is linked to the submission of the report to ISME.

LMR will administer current and future funds via an account at the University of Innsbruck.

3. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.

Completed.

4. BW to manage the compilation a formal report on the activities of the SeqCode and submit it to the ISME Executive. Publication in ISME Communications to be investigated.

Report to be finalised asap. Currently awaiting comments from MC. FV to submit it to Linda Scholten at ISME.

5. FV and LMR to compile the results of the ballot for the proposed changes to the SeqCode.

Ballot currently open until the end of June. A response rate of 33% is required. FV to contact Sabine van Wegen to ask for a reminder to be sent to Community members. Ensure that all voting members received the ballot as the original email from SurveyMonkey went to the spam folder for some of the members.

6. MC and LMR to investigate the possibility of linking the SeqCode registry to relevant entries on NCBI.

Linkout application was submitted but no response yet.

7. BW and FV to share comments on the Arahal et al. proposal published in special issue of SAM.

Commentary published in Systematic and Applied Microbiology

(<https://authors.elsevier.com/c/1jGEp2aR~NISK5>)

8. FV, LMR and MC to discuss BISMIS live discussions on Arahal et al. proposal

BW, LMR and MC presented at BISMIS Live on 18 May.

(<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1ot1DR65Tbg>).

9. MC to contact a candidate for community panel proposed by FW and submit the roundtable proposal for ISME19.

The list of people to participate in the ISME Roundtable discussion has been finalized. MC shared an outline of possible topics for discussion. The discussion should focus on the success of the SeqCode and how its operation could be improved. Feedback to MC from EB members by 8 July.

10. All to reflect and suggest on more involvement of ISME with SeqCode

Redacted

FV to contact the ISME Ambassador Program's Director, Thulani Makhalenyane to discuss the possibility on demonstrating the use of the SeqCode Registry at regional ISME meetings. MLR with the assistance of Emily St John will start with the preparation of materials that can be used and shared.

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

The ballot dealing with changes to the SeqCode has been launched and is open until the end of June. A response rate of 33% is required.

An email discussion on the advantages of including the use of an isolate as a paratype in the SeqCode will be continued on RocketChat. A paratype is defined as a specimen of an organism that helps define what the scientific name of a species and other taxon actually represents, but it is not the holotype. Minor alterations to Recommendation 19 and SeqCode section 6 would be needed to introduce this.

Standards Working Group

No new issues to report. KK will contact Emily Eloë-Fadrosh to see how the SeqCode could benefit from the current discussions related to STORMS (Strengthening the organization and reporting of microbiome studies).

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

At present 503 names have been validated and another 83 are under review.

Prof Beata Gaj from the Department of Greek and Latin Literature at the Cardinal Stefan Wyszyński University in Warsaw, Poland has joined the curation team to provide guidance on Latin naming when required.

A slide with the photos of the Curation team is available for use in presentations. Redacted

The SeqCode usage will be legally monitored using Plausible.

Redacted

Reconciliation Commission

The commission will start to address the issue of names listed in the registry that should not be treated as validly published as their type genomes do not meet the current quality requirements or they have been validated with an incorrect effective publication (e.g., taxon names proposed based on 16S rRNA genes and later described in a publication with a genome representative).

5. Discussion of Arahall et al. proposed amendments to the ICNP

BW and FV published a commentary outlining the concerns related to the Arahall et al. proposal in Systematic and Applied Microbiology. This commentary was supported by around 80 additional microbiologists from across the globe. The 34th BISMIS Live session on 18 May where BW, LMR and MC presented their views on the matter will now be followed by a presentation by ICSP members on 22 June. These sessions are recorded and will be available on the BISMIS Live YouTube channel. The session from 18 May has already been viewed 404 times, making it among the most viewed sessions on this channel.

6. DSI membership

MC will find out how the SeqCode could become a member of the DSI network.

7. EB discussion to move to Rocket Chat

The EB discussion will now formally move to RocketChat. Redacted

8. SeqCode presence on social media

It was decided that we will continue using our profile on X to promote activities of the SeqCode.

9. Conference and Meeting Updates

KK reported that the function at ASM Microbe 2024, Atlanta, was attended by around 30 people who showed interest in how to use the SeqCode.

LMR uploaded the presentation he gave at the University of Aalborg in May on the registry. Redacted

New action items

- 1.** FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.
- 2.** FV to contact Sabine van Wegen to ask for a reminder to be sent to Community members on the vote for the SeqCode amendments.
- 3.** All EB members to provide feedback on the ISME roundtable discussion document to MC by 8 July.
- 4.** FV to contact Thulani Makhalenyane to discuss the promotion of the SeqCode at regional ISME meetings. Offer the possibility of virtual tutorials on how to use the Registry.
- 5.** MLR with the assistance of Emily St John to start with the preparation of materials to demonstrate the use of the SeqCode registry at meetings.
- 6.** MC enquire about the SeqCode becoming a member of the DSI network.
- 7.** All EB members to familiarise themselves with RocketChat and to contribute to the discussion thread on the use of an isolate as a paratype in the SeqCode.

Ongoing action items

1. KK to investigate possible RCN and ICB funding.
2. PH to confirm the SeqCode funding from ISME for 2024 with Linda Scholten after the formal report has been submitted.
3. FV and LMR to compile the results of the ballot to amend the SeqCode and share it with the EB.
4. LMR to follow-up on the possibility of linking the SeqCode registry to relevant entries on NCBI.

Minutes prepared by FV: 17 June 2024

Approved: 21 June 2024